

DETERMINATION OF COTTON SELECTION VARIETIES SUITABLE FOR SOIL CONDITIONS AND REGIONAL LOCATION OF FERGANA REGION

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Annotation

Depending on the location of Fergana region and climatic conditions, cotton with medium fiber seed is planted in this area. Based on this, more emphasis should be placed on the selection of cotton varieties grown in order to obtain a large yield from the cultivated fields. Also, increasing crop productivity and productivity in the case of using a good selection variety.

Keywords: Cotton, S-6524, S-8290, Sultan, nitrogen, potassium, phosphorus, diesel fuel, temperate, continental.

Introduction

—There are 37 types of cotton in nature, many forms and varieties. All of them belong to the Malveceae family, a botanical genus called "Gossypium". Plants belonging to this family include hemp, okra, rough hemp, sedum, Chinese rose, and button-flower.

F. According to the classification of M. Mauer and A. Abdullaev, only 4 of all known wild types of cotton are cultivated. These are two diploid Old World cotton species: Gossypium-herbaseum (African-Asian cotton) and Gossypium-arbereum (Indo-Chinese cotton) and two tetraploid New World cotton species. : Gossypium-hirzutum (Mexican cotton) and Gossypium-barbadenze (Peruvian cotton).

The main goal of growing cotton is to get as much and good quality fiber from it as possible.

The main requirements for the varieties: fruitful, early, almost 80-90% of the harvest should be transferred to the first industrial variety, resistance to diseases and insects, convenient to work with machines and harvest by machine.

The quality of fiber for the textile industry must meet a number of requirements. In this case, the main technological parameters of the fiber are as follows (Table 1.2): appearance with length, hardness, thinness and relative breaking strength. The finer, thicker and longer the fiber, the better quality product is produced. Currently, more than 30 varieties are regionalized in scientific research institutes and seed farms. Cotton selection. Breeding is the science of breeding new varieties and hybrids of plants and new breeds of animals. The theoretical bases of biology, genetics and related sciences are used in carrying out selection work on cotton. The starting material includes various cultivated, wild and semi-wild types of cotton in nature [1].

Farg'ona viloyatida 2019-yil hosili uchun g'o'zaning rayonlashtirilgan va istiqbolli navlarini
JOYLASHTIRISH

ming gektar

Tib	Tumanlar nomi	Jami ekin maydoni	shu jumladan, g'o'za navlari bo'yicha					
			ertapishar navlar		jami ertapishar navlar	O'rtapishar navlar	istiqbolli navlar	yangi navlar
			Sulton	Namangan-77				
1	Yozoyovon	5,2				1,6	2,9	0,7
2	Oltinchiq	6,3		2,1	2,1		1,6	0,6
3	Qoshqepa	7,2		3,6	3,6	3,0		0,6
4	Farg'ona	5,8		2,2	2,2		1,5	0,1
5	Beshariq	8,0		4,5	4,5		2,8	0,7
6	Dang'ara	6,2	4,5		4,5		1,2	0,5
7	O'zbekiston	4,7		2,0	2,0		2,4	0,3
8	Furqat	5,4	3,5		3,5		1,5	0,4
9	Bag'dod	5,2		2,9	2,9		1,8	0,5
10	Buviyda	5,3		2,7	2,7		1,6	0,8
11	Rishton	6,0		2,6	2,6		3,0	0,4
12	Uchko'priq	5,7				2,5	2,7	0,5
13	Q'us	6,2		3,0	3,0		2,6	0,6
14	Toshloq	5,1		2,9	2,9		1,9	0,3
Jami:		82,1	8,0	28,5	36,5	7,1	31,5	7,0

Figure 1

Fergana Valley is surrounded by mountains, which prevents the direct passage of cold air masses blowing from the north and northeast and moist air masses blowing from the west. Therefore, its climate is characterized by hot, dry, long summers and mild winters. In winter, the cold air blowing from the mountains surrounding the valley accumulates in the central part of the Fergana basin.

The winter-summer air temperature in the valley decreases from the west to the east and from the central part to the hills: the average temperature in January in Kok is $-2.2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, in July it is $+27.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, in Kampirravot - $4, 8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, July is $+24.9\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. In some years, cold air masses blow from the north and northeast and pass over the mountains, causing the temperature of the valley to drop. At that time, the coldest temperature drops to $-26-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

The least rainy month is August or September in most of the valley. 2-3% of the annual rainfall is observed in these months. Only in the high mountain parts of Turkestan and Aloy mountain ranges, the least rainfall is recorded in the winter months - December, January or February, which is 3-4% of the annual rainfall.

Precipitation falls mainly in the form of snow in high mountain regions. Above 2500, the ratio of snow to rain is about the same, and below that, it rains more. The accumulation of snow in the mountains and its melting in the spring and summer to saturate the rivers is very important for irrigated agriculture.[3]

Farg'ona viloyatida 2019-yil paxta hosilini yetishtirish uchun talab etiladigan moddiy resurslar

HISOB-KITOB

ming tonna

T/r	Tumanlar nomi	paxta ekin maydoni, ming gektar	talab etiladigan moddiy resurslar				
			dizel yoqilg'isi	jami	mineral o'g'itlar (sof holda)		
					azotli	fosforli	kaliyli
1.	Yozyovon	5,2	1,3	1,9	1,3	0,4	0,2
2.	Oltiariq	6,3	1,5	2,4	1,6	0,6	0,2
3.	Qo'shtepa	7,2	1,8	2,7	1,8	0,6	0,3
4.	Farg'ona	5,8	1,3	2,1	1,4	0,5	0,2
5.	Beshariq	8,0	2,0	3,1	2,1	0,7	0,3
6.	Dang'ara	6,2	1,5	2,3	1,6	0,5	0,2
7.	O'zbekiston	4,7	1,1	1,8	1,2	0,4	0,2
8.	Furqat	5,4	1,3	2,2	1,5	0,5	0,2
9.	Bag'dod	5,2	1,3	1,9	1,3	0,4	0,2
10.	Buvayda	5,1	1,2	2,1	1,4	0,5	0,2
11.	Rishton	6,0	1,5	2,1	1,4	0,5	0,2
12.	Uchko'priq	5,7	1,4	2,3	1,6	0,5	0,2
13.	Quva	6,2	1,5	2,6	1,7	0,6	0,3
14.	Toshloq	5,1	1,3	2,0	1,3	0,5	0,2
Jami:		82,1	20,0	31,5	21,2	7,2	3,1

Figure 2

Summary

In the conditions of the Fergana Valley, it is advisable to plant seeded cotton with selection varieties such as S-6524, S-8290 and Sultan according to the above requirements. The above tables show the selection varieties planted in Fergana region and the consumption of mineral fertilizers for them. It can be seen that the consumption of mineral fertilizers for a well-chosen selection variety is not much required, in addition to the valley climate. conditions also have a great impact on the productivity of planted crops. Therefore, it is recommended to plant cotton varieties that are suitable for the climate of the region, and this can be beneficial for both the farm and the consumer. In conclusion, it should be said that alternative selection varieties for Fergana region are S-6524 and S-8290.

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